

A microstructures generation tool for virtual ply property screening of hybrid composites with high volume fractions of non-circular fibers - VIPER

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Abstract

Within the framework of *computational micromechanics* (CMM), a simulation toolset is being developed to predict the mechanical behavior of fiber-reinforced polymers from the measured properties and spatial distribution of the different phases and interfaces in the composite. Towards this end, a numerical methodology is proposed herein for the generation of 2D periodic microstructures with arbitrary fiber geometries. A major advantage of the approach presented in this work is the ability of generating high volume fractions of non-circular fibers very efficiently. The underlying algorithm is based on the minimization of fiber overlapping by dynamic translation and rotation of the fibers until intersections are eliminated. The randomness of the microstructures obtained is assessed by means of multiple spatial descriptors.

Keywords: A. Lamina/ply, B. Microstructures, C. Micro-mechanics, C. Numerical analysis

1. Introduction

Polymer matrices reinforced with high performance fibers or FRPs are preferred candidates in structural applications where the strength-to-weight ratio drives the structural design process. One of the main drawbacks regarding the use of these materials is their complex mechanical behavior, hardly predictable, which depends on the constituents properties (fibers, matrix and interfaces), as well as their spatial distribution within the material.

Virtual testing of FRP composites has been extensively developed during the last decades due to the advances in computational power. An efficient approach is the *bottom-up multiscale* strategy [1–4] which aims at predicting the mechanical behavior of the material starting from the scale of the constituents (computational micromechanics, CMM), moving up to the scale of an individual ply (computational mesomechanics), laminate, component and the final structure (computational mechanics).

Computational micromechanics has emerged in recent years as a powerful tool to predict the ply behavior under different loading conditions. This approach is based on the numerical simulation of the mechanical response of models where the constituents of the material are explicitly

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Figure 1: Cross section micrograph of a UD AS4/8552 composite with $V_f \approx 68\%$.

represented through the so called *representative volume elements* (RVE) of the composite microstructure [5]. Nevertheless, the application of appropriate boundary conditions is not trivial for such RVE models [6], and different strategies are found in the literature to analyze them. The most widely used are periodic RVEs including periodic boundary conditions (PBC) to characterize the elastic and inelastic behaviors of heterogeneous materials up to deformation localization [7–13]. It is important to note that PBC are not appropriate to study damage processes, for that purpose *embedded cell models* are often considered [14, 15]. Finally, other modelling schemes can be found such as the *extended RVE* concept developed by [16], which avoids the periodicity requirement. As a result, these numerical strategies take into account detailed information of the microstructure.

One of the main features required by the computational micromechanics strategy is the artificial generation of representative microstructures. In the case of unidirectional (UD) fiber-reinforced composites, the microstructure corresponds to the fibers cross section distribution. An example of the cross section of an AS4/8552 composite system is shown in Figure 1. Typically, aeronautic-grade fiber-reinforced composites contain very high volume fractions of circular fibers ($V_f \approx 60 \sim 70\%$). However, the numerical generation of microstructures with such high volume fractions is not trivial.

The artificial generation of microstructures has been a very demanding topic since the beginnings of computational micromechanics. A wide variety of algorithms to generate microstructures of circular fibers can be found in the literature. The simplest ones are based on the *random sequential adsorption* algorithm (RSA) [17], also known as hard-core model (HCM), which consists on the sequential insertion of fibers into the RVE at arbitrary positions such that they do not overlap each other until the desired fiber volume fraction, V_f , is reached. However, this algorithm presents a jamming limit, around $V_f = 55\%$ [18–20]. Similar strategies based on the RSA algorithm are found in the literature [21]. Bulsara et al. [22] proposed a RSA-like methodology based on optimizing the radial distribution function, $K(r)$, but the resulting microstructure was circular, an important inconvenient for its practical application to representative load cases. Some authors [7, 23] developed a modified RSA strategy to generate 3-D periodic cubic cells of spherical particles with a 50% volume fraction. This is an important achievement as the jamming

limit for homogeneous 3-D spheres assemblies through the traditional RSA approach is around 30%. The strategy followed consists of compacting the particles towards a certain point while the RVE size is reduced. This approach was translated into 2-D periodic microstructures of circular fibers up to $V_f = 65\%$ [10]. Other authors like [24] and [25] considered the fibers arrangement as a *complete spatial random* (CSR) pattern of a Poisson distribution avoiding the periodicity requirement. This approach was improved by Melro et al. [25] by applying an intermediate step stirring the fibers to generate matrix rich regions where more fibers could fit resulting in volume fractions as high as 65%. Vaughan and McCarthy [26] were able to achieve 60% fiber volume fractions by adding fibers sequentially according to the first and second nearest neighbors distribution functions obtained from the analysis of micrographs from a real microstructure. A similar approach was followed by Yang et al. [27].

This topic has been addressed within other disciplines addressing granular materials such as soils, food grains or pharmaceutical powders. A triangulation-based strategy was developed by Cui and O'Sullivan [28] to reach a high volume fraction. Nevertheless, the particles size is hardly controllable with this technique.

Another approach followed in the literature to achieve even higher fiber volume fractions consists of initially considering a regular periodic pattern of particles (square or hexagonal) and progressively apply random displacements to the fibers [16, 29, 30]. The hexagonal packaging of circular fibers reaches the maximum possible fiber volume fraction at $V_f \approx 90\%$. However, the representativeness of the microstructures obtained through this methods is limited to circular fibers.

Ghossein and Lévesque [31] implemented a different strategy, based on molecular dynamics. A fixed number of particles of zero volume are initially placed in the domain, each having a random velocity vector. The particles are then put in motion and their size increases with a given growth rate. Collisions between particles and particle-face are solved as elastic collisions during the analysis. The algorithm finishes when the particles volume fraction reaches a certain value.

Recently, Pathan et al. [32] made use of a different approach based on the minimization of a potential which is a function of the fibers overlapping. The procedure starts randomly placing the total number of fibers into the microstructure domain, regardless of fiber overlapping. Then a potential is computed based on the fibers overlapping, iteratively the fibers are displaced reducing the extension of the overlapping area. These iterations are repeated until the potential is null, i.e. no fibers are overlapping and the resulting microstructure is valid. Nevertheless, since this strategy only considers translational degrees of freedom of the fibers, is not suited for the generation of microstructures with non-circular fibers. For that purpose, the degree of freedom of fiber rotation should be included.

The central issue addressed in this work is the generation of microstructures with non-circular fibers. For this reason, most of the generation algorithms previously reviewed are not appropriate to reach high fiber volume fractions with non-conventional fiber shapes and/or heterogeneous size distributions, therefore a new strategy is proposed and described in Section 2. The randomness of some microstructures with different fiber shapes generated with this algorithm is assessed in Section 3. VIPER, a numerical tool implementing the previously described algorithm and developed within the framework of computational micromechanics by IMDEA Materials, is presented in Section 4. Final remarks and conclusions are addressed in Section 5.

2. Algorithm description

A novel versatile strategy appropriate to generate a wide variety of 2-D microstructures with high fiber volume fractions has been developed. The fibers distribution may be heterogeneous with different shapes and sizes, so virtual hybrid microstructures made of various fiber types can be represented.

Initially, the number of fibers corresponding to the target volume fraction are randomly allocated within the RVE domain, allowing overlapping. Care is taken to preserve periodicity of the microstructure fiber-wise. Then, fibers are enlarged by a tolerance magnitude specified by the user, δ , which corresponds to the minimum distance allowed between them. At this point, massive fiber overlapping is likely to occur, especially for high fiber volume fractions, see Figure 2b. The overlapping of fibers is quantified through a potential, Υ , defined as the summation of the relative overlapping areas as,

$$\Upsilon = \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \sum_{j>i}^N \frac{A_{ij}}{A_i} \quad (1)$$

where A_i is the cross section of fiber i , and A_{ij} is the intersecting area of fibers i and j .

The next step is to reduce the overlapping of fibers. This problem can be addressed in different ways, e.g. following an optimization scheme [32]. In this work, this process is accomplished applying a dynamic scheme by considering overlaps as collisions of rigid bodies [33]. In this manner, each fiber is treated as a rigid body that can not only move, but also rotate which is crucial for the case of non-circular fibers. Overlapping is then reduced by repelling the fibers iteratively. Linear (v_i^t) and angular velocities (ω_i^t) of every fiber i are updated at every increment t following an explicit scheme as,

$$v_i^{t+1} = v_i^t + \frac{\Delta t}{m_i} F_i^t \quad (2a)$$

$$\omega_i^{t+1} = \omega_i^t + \frac{\Delta t}{I_i} M_i^t \quad (2b)$$

where Δt is the time step of the explicit scheme, m_i and I_i are the mass and rotational inertia of fiber i , and F_i^t and M_i^t are the force and moment applied on fiber i . The linear force F_i is made of two contributions: a component F_i^{repel} which intends to reduce fiber overlaps (repelling force), and a viscous term F_i^{visc} which slows down the fiber velocity to prevent rebounds and oscillations. Similar terms are identified in the angular moment term M_i . The process is illustrated in Figure 2.

The fibers repelling algorithm was incorporated by means of the free open source 2-D physics simulator engine Box2D [33]. This library was originally developed by Erin Catto and published under the zlib license. An important advantage of this approach is its high efficiency, being up to two orders of magnitude faster compared to [32].

Once the potential is lower than a tolerance specified ($\Upsilon < \Upsilon_{\min}$), i.e. fibers overlapping is minimal, the iterative process is finished. It must be remarked that if the repelling process does not converge, i.e. fibers overlaps cannot be solved, the generation process is cancelled and the algorithm restarts again, fiber overlaps are not neglected. A low value of Υ_{\min} should be selected to minimize its influence on the fibers distribution. For instance, $\Upsilon_{\min} = 10^{-3}$ is sufficient to keep residual overlaps below $\delta_{res} \approx 0.01 d/N_{ov}$, where N_{ov} is the number of overlaps along the whole microstructure. To guarantee a minimum distance in between adjacent fibers and avoid residual overlaps, size of fibers is reduced by the tolerance magnitude specified initially,

Figure 2: Illustration of the microstructures generation algorithm applied to 2-lobular fibers with $V_f = 65\%$: a) evolution of the fibers overlapping residual as a function of the number of iterations, b) initial positions of the fibers, c) fibers position at iteration 19, d) final position of the fibers after potential minimization (iteration 96), and e) final microstructure after fibers shrinking.

$\tilde{\delta}$, see Figure 2e. Typically, this value is very small compared to the fibers diameter, $\tilde{\delta} \ll d$, and it is necessary to facilitate, for instance, the meshing process required by a finite element analysis of the microstructure. This and other finite element modeling features are thoroughly addressed in [9, 11, 26, 34]. Very small gaps in between adjacent fibers would require a very fine discretization, what would increase considerably the computational cost.

3. Statistical analysis

Through the use of the algorithm presented above, statistical analyses are carried out to assess the representativeness of microstructures of various non-circular fiber shapes. The statistical metrics are compared with the ideal Poisson dispersion of fibers, i.e. *complete spatial random* (CSR). The meaningful statistical descriptors to be analyzed are the following:

- Execution time, t_{exec} .
- Local volume fraction, V_f^{loc} .
- Voronoi cells area, c_v .
- Nearest-neighbors distance, δ_1 and δ_2 .
- Nearest-neighbor orientation, θ_1 .
- Second order intensity function, $K(r)$.
- Radial distribution function, $g(r)$.
- Two-point probability function, $S_2(\mathbf{x})$.

The microstructures generated and analyzed have a constant fiber volume fraction of $V_f = 65\%$. The fibers size is not homogeneous, instead a normal distribution with a standard deviation of 5% of the effective fiber diameter, d , is selected to introduce another source of variability. A minimum distance between fibers was specified with a value of $\tilde{\delta} = d/40$.

The size of the RVE is approximately 12 times the equivalent diameter of the fibers, $L = 12d$, which is large enough to produce distributions in which the influence of the periodic boundaries is negligible [24]. It should be noted that although the microstructures analyzed in this section are periodic, the generation algorithm presented in Section 2 can be adapted to produce non-periodic fiber distributions for other modelling approaches.

The fiber cross sections considered for this study are the following: lobular with 2, 3 and 4 lobes; polygonal fibers with smoothed vertices (Spolygons), with 3 and 4 edges ($\chi = 0.25$); elliptical fibers ($\epsilon = 0.75$); C-shaped fibers ($\theta = 90^\circ$ and $\xi = 0.15$); and circular fibers for reference. An example of each virtual microstructure configuration is shown in Figure 3. Details of the geometry of the non-circular fibers can be found in Appendix A.

3.1. Execution time, t_{exec}

The RVEs generation algorithm was implemented in Python 2.7 and it runs in a single CPU of an Intel® Xeon® Processor E5-2680.

The execution time t_{exec} is reported in order to illustrate the additional computational effort required to deal with complex fiber geometries compared to the reference circular ones. This

Figure 3: Illustration of one microstructure with each of the fiber shapes considered with $L = 50 \mu\text{m}$ and $V_f = 65\%$: a) circular, b) lobular-2, c) lobular-3, d) lobular-4, e) spolygon-3, f) spolygon-4, g) elliptical and h) c-shaped.

value is reported not only for the reference case, with RVE size $L = 12d$, but also for larger RVEs ($L = 20d$ and $50d$). The results are reported in Table 1.

The lowest execution time is obtained for the microstructures of circular fibers, as expected. Computation of the fibers intersection is the most time consuming task of the generation algorithm, therefore, concave and complex cross sections increase the computational cost noticeably. It is observed that the execution time raises with the number of geometrical features of the fiber section, for instance, microstructures of lobular fibers with 4 lobes are slower to generate than those with 2 and 3 lobes, as it happens with the smoothed polygonal fibers. C-shaped fibers present the most complex geometry and in some cases present convergence issues related to their concave cross section. This effect gets more accused for larger RVEs. Nevertheless, compared to the reference circular fibers, the execution time remains in the same order of magnitude, with

Table 1: Average execution times for the generation of microstructures with $V_f = 65\%$ for different fiber shapes and three RVE sizes. The number of fibers for the three RVE sizes is approximately 120, 330 and 2070, respectively. Standard deviation values are shown in parenthesis.

Fiber	Execution time, t_{exec} [s]		
	$L = 12d$	$L = 20d$	$L = 50d$
Circular	2.6 (0.4)	5.9 (0.9)	35 (3)
2-Lobular	4.2 (0.7)	11.3 (1.6)	70 (14)
3-Lobular	4.9 (0.8)	11.8 (1.6)	76 (16)
4-Lobular	6.2 (1.1)	15.8 (4.2)	98 (15)
Spolygon-3	4.9 (0.8)	12.1 (2.6)	81 (10)
Spolygon-4	6.2 (2.2)	13.1 (2.9)	86 (12)
Elliptical	4.1 (0.4)	11.1 (1.4)	69 (13)
C-shaped	6.5 (1.1)	23 (4)	140 (21)

Figure 4: Local volume fraction description: a) computation of the V_f^{loc} at P with $s_r/d = 4$, and b) resulting field over the whole RVE with $V_f = 65\%$.

increment ratios between 1.5 and up to 4 for the case of C-shaped fibers.

Although the algorithm presented in this work is $O(N^2)$ for a very high number of fibers, for RVEs considered in this section, where $N = 120, 330$ and 2040 , it is approximately $O(N)$. The explanation for this is that the computation of the overlapping area (A_{ij}) is done in two steps: a first check to determine if the fibers are sufficiently close for overlapping to be possible, followed by the calculation of A_{ij} only for those cases. The cost of the algorithm can be expressed as $t = \tilde{t}_{\text{overlap}} \cdot N + \tilde{t}_{\text{range}} \cdot N^2$, where $\tilde{t}_{\text{overlap}}$ is the average time required to calculate $\sum_{j>i}^{n_{\text{range}}} A_{ij}$ and \tilde{t}_{range} is the average time required to determine whether the fibers i and j are sufficiently close. Since $\tilde{t}_{\text{overlap}} \gg \tilde{t}_{\text{range}}$, the cost of the algorithm is $O(N)$ for low numbers of fibers (up to few thousands), whereas for a larger amount of fibers its cost is $O(N^2)$. Thus, the effect of the RVE size on the computation time for the cases presented herein is $O(N) = O(L^2)$.

The execution times are considered sufficient for the generation of RVEs containing a few hundred or even thousands of fibers, as it is the case of this work. The efficiency could be greatly improved by the use of a compiled programming language (e.g. C++) with parallelization capabilities or introducing some modifications in the implementation strategy, such as precomputing estimators for A_{ij} .

3.2. Local volume fraction, V_f^{loc}

The local fiber volume fraction is usually represented as a scalar field on the spatial domain of the microstructure, V_f^{loc} , and can be calculated at any point $P(x, y)$ of the RVE for a given sampling radius, s_r , as the fiber volume fraction within the circle of center P and radius s_r . Figure 4a illustrates the procedure to compute $V_f^{\text{loc}}(x, y; s_r)$ in a microstructure of circular fibers with $V_f = 65\%$ and $s_r = 4d$. Since the microstructure is periodic, there is no need to correct the edge effect as it is always possible to measure the volume fraction of the fibers falling into the region of interest. The resulting local volume fraction field is plotted in Figure 4b. It is observed that the limits of V_f^{loc} , 58.5 and 69% respectively, bound the mean value V_f . This dependence of the maximum and minimum local volume fraction on the sampling radius can be read as a means to detect matrix rich regions and fiber clusters.

The upper and lower bounds of the local volume fraction field are presented as statistical descriptors. The dependency of these bounds on the sampling radius, s_r , is shown in Figure 5a for the case of circular fibers. For very small s_r values, matrix rich regions are identified as the areas with the lowest local fiber volume fraction, as it is observed in Figure 5c, while areas with closely packed fibers read volume fraction values higher than the average, V_f . Nevertheless, for higher s_r values, both upper and lower bounds follow an asymptotic trend towards the average fiber volume fraction (see Figure 5d). As suggested previously, the local volume fraction descriptor can be employed to detect resin rich areas whose size is larger than the sampling radius used.

The V_f^{loc} vs. s_r curves for the rest of the fiber cross sections are shown in Figure 5b. All of them observe the same trend and overlap, so it can be concluded that similar results in terms of fiber clustering or resin pockets are observed. This can be easily explained by the high fiber volume fraction under consideration in this study.

3.3. Voronoi cells area, c_v

The RVE is divided in cells by a Voronoi tessellation in which the particle centers act as seeds, such that every point of the cell is closer to its center than the others. An efficient scheme to compute the Voronoi tessellation consists of the Bowyer-Watson algorithm [35, 36]. Based on the Voronoi cells area, the coefficient of variation c_v is defined as,

$$c_v = \frac{\text{std}(A_v^i)}{\text{mean}(A_v^i)} \quad (3)$$

where A_v^i represents the Voronoi cell area of fiber i , 'mean' and 'std' are the arithmetic mean and standard deviation of the population. The coefficient of variation is a statistical descriptor that quantifies the randomness in the spatial distribution of the fibers. For instance, regular fiber arrangements, such as hexagonal or rectangular, present $c_v = 0$; whereas a high c_v suggests higher randomness in the fibers distribution.

Figure 6 collects the distribution of c_v from 10 realizations on each microstructure type. The box plots are intended to describe the population of the variable of interest, in this case c_v , by means of the quartiles. The box encloses the Q1 and Q3 quartiles, whereas the red line represents the median of the distribution (Q2). The coefficients of variation obtained are in the range between 0.12 and 0.25. These values are reasonably high for such dense fiber volume fraction ($V_f = 65\%$), compared to other results reported in the literature for similar volume fractions [30]. It is observed that circular fibers show the lowest c_v values, compared to the rest of the fibers. On the other hand, the lobular-2 fibers exhibit the highest coefficient of variation due to their high aspect ratio.

3.4. Nearest-neighbors distance, δ_1 and δ_2

The nearest-neighbors distance descriptors are shown through the *probability density function* (PDF) of the distances between one fiber and its first and second nearest neighbors, δ_1 and δ_2 respectively [37]. This statistical metric informs about the short-distance interaction between fibers. The results obtained for the RVEs under analysis are plotted in Figure 7. The PDFs are obtained using the kernel density estimation (KDE) based on normal distributions [38]. It is important to note that the minimum allowable distance between adjacent fibers is $\tilde{\delta} = d/40$, the vertical grey line on the plots represents this tolerance distance.

As expected, all of the microstructures observe narrow distributions of δ_1/d close to the minimum tolerance distance, $\tilde{\delta}$. Whereas the second nearest-neighbor distributions present higher

Figure 5: Analysis of the local volume fraction as a function of the sampling radius, s_r : a) upper and lower bounds of V_f^{loc} for 10 microstructures with circular fibers, b) comparison of the results for all the fiber cross sections under analysis, c) local fiber volume fraction field of a microstructure of 3-lobular fibers with $s_r/d = 2$ and d) $s_r/d = 8$.

Figure 6: Coefficients of variation, c_v , for the microstructures studied. Distributions obtained from 10 equivalent realizations.

scatter. Regarding, the fiber shape effect on this descriptor, it is observed that concave fibers (lobular and c-shaped) exhibit a higher dispersion in both, first and second, nearest-neighbor distances. Indeed, for lobular fibers the nearest-neighbor distances decrease slightly as the number of lobes increases, due to the higher number of concave-convex entanglements.

3.5. Nearest-neighbor direction, θ_1

The direction in which the nearest-neighbor is found, θ_1 , can be used to complement the description of the nearest-neighbor fiber distance metric and the observation of preference directions, if any. In this case, the *cumulative distribution function* (CDF) of fiber orientation is employed to represent this statistical descriptor.

The CDF of θ_1 is plotted in Figure 8. A CSR distribution would be represented as a straight line, standing for the fact that finding the nearest-neighbor in all the directions is equally likely to occur. In spite of the high fiber volume fraction, it is observed that all of the microstructures generated are approximately perfectly random, as they follow the same trend of the theoretical CSR distribution (dashed line). For microstructures with extremely high values of fiber volume fraction ($V_f > 80\%$) it is expected to observe preferred orientations representing the hexagonal packaging of fibers throughout the RVE.

3.6. Second order intensity function, $K(r)$

The second-order intensity function, or Ripley's K -function, provides insight about the pattern distribution of fibers from short to long range distances [39], and can be used to characterize fiber clustering in a microstructure [22]. It is defined as the ratio between the number of extra

Figure 7: Probability density functions (PDFs) of the first and second nearest-neighbors distances, δ_1 and δ_2 , for the different microstructure cases over 10 realizations. The minimum distance between adjacent fibers was set to $\delta/d = 0.025$.

Figure 8: Cumulative density function (CDF) of the nearest-neighbor direction for the different microstructure cases over 10 realizations. The ideal CDF of a complete spatial random distribution, CSR, is shown as reference (dashed line).

fibers expected to lie within a radial distance r of an arbitrary point and the actual number of fibers within that area, i.e.

$$K(r) = \frac{1}{N \cdot N_a} \sum_{i=1}^N \hat{I}_i(r) \quad (4)$$

wherein N is the number of fibers in the RVE, N_a is the average number of fibers per unit area $N_a = N/A$, and $\hat{I}_i(r)$ is an indicator function which is 1 when the center of fiber i lies within r distance from the reference point, and 0 otherwise.

The calculation of the K -function from a non periodic microstructure requires taking into account edge effects [40]. Nevertheless, the application of equation 4 to a periodic microstructure is straightforward, as the RVE can be replicated in the two $x - y$ directions as many times as necessary. To quantify the randomness in the fibers distribution throughout the microstructure, the resulting K -function is compared to that of a reference 2-D CSR dispersion,

$$\hat{K}_{\text{ref}}(r) = \pi r^2 \quad (5)$$

A proper comparison of \hat{K} with \hat{K}_{ref} can be achieved by transforming equation 4 into Besag's L -function [41].

$$\hat{L}(r) = \sqrt{\frac{\hat{K}(r)}{\pi}} - r \quad (6)$$

It is easily observed that $\hat{L} = 0$ for CSR-like distributions. For interpretation, positive values of $\hat{L}(r)$ indicate clustering over that spatial scale whereas negative values indicate dispersion.

In Figure 9, the resulting L -functions obtained for the microstructures with circular fibers (Figure 9a) and for the non-circular fiber cross sections (Figure 9b) are represented. The results of a regular microstructure with the typical hexagonal pattern are shown to illustrate the effect of a regular fiber pattern on the L -function, where the sharp peaks and troughs evidence regularity

Figure 9: Besag's functions, $\hat{L}(r/d)$: a) comparison of a random microstructure with a regular hexagonal pattern, and b) analysis of microstructures with non-circular fibers.

in the fibers distribution. On the other hand, the microstructure generated with the proposed methodology (solid line) shows the typical features of a random dispersion of fibers: an initial peak around $r/d = 1$, followed by some oscillations with an approximate period of $r/d \approx 1$, which progressively decays to $\hat{L} \rightarrow 0$ for $r/d \geq 5$. The same features are observed for the non-circular fibers, verifying the long range randomness in the fibers distributions.

3.7. Radial distribution function, $g(r)$

The radial distribution function, $g(r)$, computes the probability of finding the center of a fiber at a given distance r from the center of another particle. It is calculated by determining the number of fibers lying within an annular region of inner radius, r , and thickness, dr , divided by the average number of fibers per unit area, N_a [42]. Taking advantage of the K -function computed previously (equation 5), the radial distribution function can be written as,

$$g(r) = \frac{1}{N_a 2\pi r} \frac{dK(r)}{dr} \quad (7)$$

By definition, the radial distribution function of a CSR distribution is $g(r) = 1$. Thus, a random dispersion of fibers will tend to 1 for large enough values of r .

The radial distribution functions computed based on the K -functions from the previous section are shown in Figure 10. The $g(r)$ function obtained from a regular hexagonal pattern of circular fibers is plotted in Figure 10a (dashed line), observing abrupt oscillations which evidence regularity in the dispersion of fibers. Nonetheless, a random dispersion of fibers result in a characteristic $g(r)$ function as shown by the solid line: initially, a sharp peak denotes the presence of the first nearest-neighbor ($r/d \approx 1$); followed by some oscillations representing the next rows of neighboring fibers ($r/d \approx 2, 3, 4 \dots$), which finally decay towards $g = 1$. The same analysis was carried out for the microstructures with non-circular fiber shapes (see Figure 10b). Regardless of the fiber cross section, randomness in the fibers distribution is evidenced for long distances ($r/d \geq 5$).

Figure 10: Radial distribution function $g(r/d)$: a) comparison of random distribution of circular fibers with an hexagonal regular arrangement, and b) comparison of $g(r)$ for microstructures with different fiber shapes.

3.8. Two-point probability function, $S_2(\mathbf{x})$

The two-point probability function, $S_2^{ij}(\mathbf{x}_A, \mathbf{x}_B)$, quantifies the probability of finding simultaneously the phase i and the phase j at two arbitrarily chosen points \mathbf{x}_A and \mathbf{x}_B , respectively, and can be formulated as [43],

$$S_2^{ij}(\mathbf{x}_A, \mathbf{x}_B) = \langle \chi^i(\mathbf{x}_A, \alpha) \cdot \chi^j(\mathbf{x}_B, \alpha) \rangle \quad (8)$$

where the symbol $\langle \cdot \rangle$ denotes the ensemble average of the product of characteristic functions $\chi^i(\mathbf{x}_A, \alpha)$ which are equal to one when the point \mathbf{x}_A lies in the phase i in the sample α and equal to zero otherwise:

$$\chi^i(\mathbf{x}_A, \alpha) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \mathbf{x}_A \in D^i(\alpha) \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

$D^i(\alpha)$ represents the domain covered by phase i . In general, the evaluation of the characteristic functions for the computation of the S_2 function may be prohibitively costly. Nevertheless, assuming *statistical homogeneity* of the microstructure and validity of the *ergodic hypothesis*, the two-point probability function becomes only dependent on the relative position of $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}_B - \mathbf{x}_A$ [43, 44], and is written as,

$$S_2^{ij}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{|\Omega|} \int_{\Omega} \chi^i(\mathbf{x}, \alpha) \cdot \chi^j(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{y}, \alpha) d\mathbf{y} \quad (10)$$

where $|\Omega|$ stands for the area of the sample analyzed. Several sampling methods were devised to determine the values of the two-point probability function, such as techniques based on the Monte-Carlo method. A more refined approach is the sampling template technique to sample isotropic microstructures [45]. To this end, a pixel-like discretization of the microstructure $W \times H$ bitmap is considered, as in Figure 11a. The pixel size selected was $0.5 \mu\text{m}$, however, for clarity purposes, in Figure 11a it is shown with $1 \mu\text{m}$. In addition, considering that the microstructure is periodic, equation 10 reduces to

$$S_2^f(m, n) = \frac{1}{WH} \sum_{i=1}^W \sum_{j=1}^H \chi^f(i, j) \cdot \chi^f((i+m) \% W, (j+n) \% H) \quad (11)$$

where $\%$ represents the *modulo* operator, and f represents the fiber phase, with S_2^f abbreviating S_2^{ff} . The summation in equation 11 requires an enormous number of operations, $O(W^2H^2)$. For that reason, in this work the more efficient Fourier transform procedure developed by Berryman [46] is employed to sample the two-point probability function as,

$$S_2^f(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{WH} \text{IDFT} \{ \text{DFT} \{ \chi^f(\mathbf{x}) \} \cdot \overline{\text{DFT} \{ \chi^f(\mathbf{x}) \}} \} \quad (12)$$

wherein DFT and IDFT stand for the *discrete Fourier transform*, and its inverse; and \bar{B} stands for the complex conjugate of B . The number of operations needed to compute equation 12 is only $O(WH \log(WH) + WH)$ [46]. The calculations were performed by means of the scientific library of Python: `scipy` [47].

The resulting S_2^f field of a random periodic microstructure is shown in Figure 11b. A peak of value $S_2^f = V_f$ is observed at each of the corners, representing the periodicity feature. Whereas, in the rest of the domain it drops to a plateau around $S_2^f = V_f^2$, evidencing that there are no long-range correlations in the system, so falling of the two ends of vector \mathbf{x} into the fiber phase are independent events, each with a probability equals to V_f .

Since the two-point probability function is a scalar field, its analysis requires its projection on a surface in order to visualize a curve. To do that, the S_2^f field has been projected onto planes in different directions with respect to the horizontal x_1 ($\phi = \text{const}$) and cylindrical surfaces at a constant distance from the origin ($|\mathbf{x}| = \text{const}$) as illustrated in Figure 11b. The typical curves obtained from the fiber direction analysis, $\phi = \text{const}$, are plotted in Figure 11c. For all ϕ values there is an initial peak at $|\mathbf{x}| = 0$, since the probability to find a zero-length vector (i.e. a point) on the fiber phase is equal to the fiber volume fraction, V_f . For $\phi = 0$ and 90° , the same peak is observed at $|\mathbf{x}| = L$, as a result of the RVE periodicity. The plateau encountered has a value around $S_2^f = V_f^2$, as explained previously. This set of curves demonstrate the quasi-isotropic distribution of fibers in the microstructure, since there are no remarkable differences between ϕ curves.

Regarding the radial analysis, $|\mathbf{x}| = \text{const}$, a constant value of V_f is obtained at $|\mathbf{x}| = 0$ as expected. The rest of $|\mathbf{x}|$ values experiment a constant expectancy value at $S_2^f = V_f^2$. Again, the microstructure periodicity is evidenced for $|\mathbf{x}| = L$ at $\phi = 0$ and 90° .

In the case of patterned microstructures, intense peaks and troughs are generated along the S_2^f field. This is illustrated for a regular hexagonal and square patterns in Figures 12a and b respectively. These fiber arrangements show a regular dispersion of peaks located at the corresponding fiber centers, indicating the presence of preferred \mathbf{x} vectors.

The analysis of the microstructures by means of the two-point probability function is collected in Figures 12c and d. All the microstructures show the same features as described for the circular fibers RVE: $S_2^f = V_f^2$ for all the domain excepting the RVE corners where its value is V_f . The only difference found lies in the $\phi = \text{const}$ analysis, where the decay rate for small \mathbf{x} is slightly different depending on the fiber cross section. This suggests a different entanglement between adjacent fibers due to their convex-concave geometry as shown in the detail in Figure 12c. It is worth noting that similar findings can be derived from the radial distribution function $g(r/d)$ for the case of isotropic microstructures, see Figure b10b.

Figure 11: Two-point probability function: a) Bitmap discretization of a microstructure with circular fibers, b) S_2^f probability field in the 2D space, c) projection of S_2^f along different orientations ($\phi = \text{const}$), and d) projection of S_2^f along various distances ($|\mathbf{x}| = \text{const}$).

Figure 12: Two-point probability functions of various microstructures: S_2^f fields of regular circular fiber arrangements a) hexagonal and b) square, and results for microstructures with non-circular fibers for c) $\phi = 45^\circ$ and d) $|\mathbf{x}| = 30 \mu\text{m}$.

4. Towards Virtual ply proPERty screening: VIPER

The algorithm presented in this work for the generation of hybrid microstructures with high fiber volume fractions and arbitrary fiber sections was implemented in a licensed software tool specially developed to expedite composites Virtual ply proPERty screening, called VIPER. In this work, only the generation tool of a micromechanical framework is presented, nevertheless, the final goal of the microstructures produced is to compute the properties required by the user (e.g. mechanical, electrical, thermal), and to assess the influence of any variable such as the shape of the fibers, their relative size, the potential synergies between fibers of different materials in hybrid composites, etc.

VIPER is a ready-to-use software package, developed using Python, which includes a *Graphical User Interface* and takes advantage of the Box2D library [33] to carry out the fiber repelling process described in Section 2. It also includes capabilities to calculate the statistical descriptors employed in Section 3: local volume fraction, Voronoi cells area, nearest-neighbors distance, nearest-neighbors orientation, second order intensity function, radial distribution function, and two-point probability function. Other generation algorithms are available in VIPER such as the *random sequential adsorption* (RSA, [7]) and the *nearest-neighbor algorithm* (NNA, [26]). Nevertheless, these algorithms are not suited to reach high fiber volume fractions ($V_f > 50\%$) in microstructures with non-circular fibers.

An important and very time consuming phase of any analysis in CMM is building up the finite element (FE) model. To speed up this stage and enable the study of models containing hundreds or thousands of fibers, VIPER is able to generate FE models through Abaqus [48], as illustrated in Figure 13. Periodicity would then be exploited by applying PBC. The example is just shown for demonstration purposes, the toolset is also able to generate 2-D and 3-D microstructures extruded along the fibers direction or following some parametric curves as in [13]. Analysis of 2-D microstructures with circular and non-circular fibers can be found in [11, 12].

As an example of properties screening, the transverse elastic properties of the microstructures presented in Section 3 were calculated by FE in Abaqus using PBC. The fibers and matrix are considered to behave as linear elastic solids. The matrix is isotropic with an elastic modulus of $E^m = 5.07$ GPa and a Poisson ratio of $\nu^m = 0.35$ [12]. Whereas, the fibers are assumed to be made of carbon, thus transversely isotropic with elastic moduli $E_1 = 230$ GPa and $E_2 = E_3 = 13$ GPa; shear moduli $G_{12} = G_{13} = 11$ GPa; Poisson ratios $\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.3$ and $\nu_{23} = 0.46$ [10], where 1 is the direction of the fibers, and 2-3 define the isotropy plane. Since a minimum clearance is guaranteed in between fibers, they are completely surrounded by matrix. For more details about the numerical assumptions and details of the FE model, the reader is referred to previous works of the authors [11, 34]. The transverse elastic properties of 10 realizations of each kind of microstructure are summarized in Table 2. The results evidence the high level of transverse isotropy of the microstructures produced, the transverse moduli in the horizontal (E_2) and vertical (E_3) directions only differ in about 0.5%, and the shear modulus (G_{23}) is within a 2% error compared to the theoretical value $\tilde{G}_{23} = E_2/(1 + \nu_{23})/2$. On the other hand, the identical fiber volume fractions of all the different microstructures results in equivalent elastic properties of all of them. Therefore, if the fibers are evenly distributed, their cross section does not affect the elastic properties of the microstructure.

Figure 13: Main window of the user interface of VIPER with an example of a hybrid microstructure combining different non-circular fibers and 3D FE model generated through Abaqus [48].

5. Concluding remarks

Although several algorithms to generate 2D microstructures with high fiber volume fractions have been previously developed and are reported in the literature, none of them is suited to generate microstructures with non-circular fibers. Hence, this paper proposes a novel strategy to artificially generate hybrid microstructures with high fiber volume fractions and arbitrary fiber sections. The approach was demonstrated to efficiently generate statistically random periodic microstructures with a wide variety of fiber shapes, including concave cross sections (e.g. lobular, c-shaped). The ability to generate such complex microstructures enables the exploration of a vast design space and potentially the development of composites with improved ply properties. The algorithm was integrated in a user-friendly software tool specially developed to expedite composites Virtual ply proPERty screening, called VIPER.

6. Acknowledgements

The research leading to these results has received funding from the Spanish Ministry of Industry, Economy and Competitiveness (MINECO) through project HYDTCOMP (MAT2015-69491-C03-02), from AIRBUS S.A.S. (France) through the project SIMSCREEN (Simulation for Screening Composite Materials Properties) and from Airbus Operations S.L. (Spain) through the project incubator NONCIRC (Non-Circular Carbon Fibres). C.S. Lopes also acknowledges the support of MINECO through the *Ramón y Cajal* fellowship (grant RYC-2013-14271).

Table 2: Transverse elastic properties of 10 realizations of the microstructures generated with $V_f = 65\%$ and $L = 12d$ for different fiber shapes. Standard deviation values are shown in parenthesis.

Fiber	Elastic properties			
	E_2 [GPa]	E_3 [GPa]	ν_{23} [-]	G_{23} [GPa]
Circular	8.26 (0.03)	8.27 (0.05)	0.2948 ($8 \cdot 10^{-4}$)	3.132 ($9 \cdot 10^{-3}$)
2-Lobular	8.33 (0.05)	8.36 (0.06)	0.2953 ($8 \cdot 10^{-4}$)	3.150 ($11 \cdot 10^{-3}$)
3-Lobular	8.36 (0.06)	8.37 (0.03)	0.2955 ($7 \cdot 10^{-4}$)	3.160 ($17 \cdot 10^{-3}$)
4-Lobular	8.37 (0.06)	8.39 (0.04)	0.2954 ($6 \cdot 10^{-4}$)	3.160 ($13 \cdot 10^{-3}$)
Spolygon-3	8.33 (0.05)	8.36 (0.07)	0.2958 ($13 \cdot 10^{-4}$)	3.160 ($14 \cdot 10^{-3}$)
Spolygon-4	8.35 (0.05)	8.35 (0.06)	0.2952 ($10 \cdot 10^{-4}$)	3.160 ($13 \cdot 10^{-3}$)
Elliptical	8.37 (0.05)	8.41 (0.06)	0.2961 ($8 \cdot 10^{-4}$)	3.170 ($10 \cdot 10^{-3}$)
C-shaped	8.34 (0.03)	8.33 (0.02)	0.2950 ($8 \cdot 10^{-4}$)	3.149 ($8 \cdot 10^{-3}$)

Appendix A. Geometry of non-circular fibers

A summary of the geometrical details of each of the families of fibers considered in this work is summarized in Table A.3 together with the corresponding schematics displayed in Figure A.14. Each of these fiber cross sections are defined by at least one shape parameter (e.g. number of edges) and its area, by means of the effective diameter, d . In all cases, d_c corresponds to the diameter of the circumscribing circumference of the non-circular section. The center of the fibers is defined by the point O , however auxiliary points are identified in some cases as O' and O'' .

Figure A.14: Graphical description of the geometry of each of the families of non-circular fibers: a) lobular, b) spolygonal, c) elliptical, and d) C-shaped with $\theta = 220^\circ$ and $\xi = 0.4$ for illustration. See Table A.3 for details.

Table A.3: Summary of the geometrical description of the fibers. For a complete description of the non-circular geometries, the reader is referred to [49].

Fiber	Input parameter	Geometrical relations
Circular	d : effective diameter	$d_c = d$
Lobular (Figure A.14a)	d : effective diameter n_l : number of lobes $(n_l \geq 2)$	$\alpha = \pi/n_l, \gamma = \pi/6 = 30^\circ$ $d_c = d \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{(1+\csc \alpha)^2 \cdot (\cot \alpha + \sqrt{3} + \alpha)}}$ $r = \frac{d_c}{2(1+\csc \alpha)}, \hat{r} = r \cdot \csc \alpha$ $\tilde{r} = r \cdot (\cot \alpha + \sqrt{3})$
S-polygon (Figure A.14b)	d : effective diameter n_e : number of edges $(n_e \geq 3)$ χ : smoothing ratio $(0 < \chi < 1)$	$\alpha = \pi/n_e, \chi = R/a$ $d_c = d \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{\frac{n_e}{2} \sin 2\alpha - \chi^2 \cdot (n_e \cdot \tan \alpha - \pi)}}$ $r = d_c/2$ $\hat{r} = \frac{r}{1-\chi \cdot (1-\cos \alpha)}$
Elliptical (Figure A.14c)	d : effective diameter ϵ : eccentricity $(0 < \epsilon < 1)$	$d_c = d \cdot (1 - \epsilon^2)^{-1/4}$ $a = d_c/2$ $b = a \cdot \sqrt{1 - \epsilon^2}$
C-shaped (Figure A.14d)	d : effective diameter θ : angular amplitude $(0 < \theta < 2\pi)$ ξ : hollowness ratio $(0 < \xi < 1)$	$d_c = d \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{\frac{\theta}{2}(1-\xi^2) + \frac{\pi}{4}(1-\xi)^2}}$ $R_o = d/2$ $\xi = R_i/R_o$ $R_m = (R_o + R_i)/2$ $r = (R_o - R_i)/2$ $\Delta > 2r \Rightarrow \sin \frac{\theta}{2} > \frac{1-\xi}{1+\xi}$

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